

Research Article

Assessment of charcoal as energy source for cooking among households in Zaria local government area, Kaduna state

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Abstract

Access to affordable, efficient, and environmentally sustainable cooking energy remains a major challenge in Nigeria. Despite national efforts to expand access to electricity and promote cleaner fuels, this study was conducted to assess the utilization, and factors influencing the use of charcoal as a cooking energy source among households in Zaria. A total of 150 structured questionnaires were administered across five wards to gather data on demographic characteristics of, charcoal use and associated challenges. The results revealed that 60% of respondents use charcoal as their primary or supplementary cooking fuel, citing affordability, ease of access, and cultural familiarity as key reasons. Chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association between monthly income and charcoal use ($P \leq 0.005$), affirming that lower-income households are more likely to rely on charcoal. Logistic regression further highlighted that male-headed households were significantly less likely to use charcoal than female-headed ones (Odd Ratio (OR) = 0.45; $p = 0.029$), indicating gender-linked disparities in energy vulnerability. Additionally, households earning above ₦60,000 were 4.67 times more likely to use charcoal than those earning below ₦30,000 ($p = 0.001$), a finding that may reflect the transitional use of cleaner charcoal forms over firewood. Despite charcoal's benefits such as reduced smoke and convenience, respondents also cited health (30%) and environmental concerns (16.7%) as drawbacks. Charcoal remains a dominant cooking fuel among lower-income households in Zaria due to economic constraints and infrastructure limitations. Targeted interventions such as liquefied petroleum gas subsidies, promotion of improved cook stoves, awareness campaigns, and sustainable charcoal production policies, will be essential for achieving Nigeria's clean energy transition goals and reducing health and environmental burdens associated with traditional biomass use.

Keywords: Charcoal, Cooking Energy, Household Energy Use, Biomass, Energy Poverty, Sustainable Development

1. Introduction

Access to affordable, efficient, and environmentally sustainable energy sources for cooking remains a significant challenge in many developing countries, including Nigeria (Oyedepo, 2014). Despite efforts to expand access to electricity and promote cleaner fuels, a substantial proportion of households still rely on traditional biomass fuels such as firewood and charcoal for daily cooking needs (NBS, 2021). In Nigeria, biomass, comprising firewood, charcoal, and agricultural residues remains the dominant source of cooking energy, especially in rural and peri-urban areas. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2021), over 70% of households rely on biomass, with firewood accounting for

the largest share. The increase in population growth, urban development and expansion has also increased pressure on demand for domestic energy (Madlener, and Sunak, 2011). Even though this traditional biomass used as fuels are not only inefficient but have continued to contribute to deforestation, environmental degradation, and indoor air pollution, which poses serious adverse health especially for women and children (WHO, 2020). This has exacerbated the pressure on natural resources, leading to unsustainable energy practices (Atteridge, Heneen, and Sinyangwe, 2022).

The dependence on traditional biomass fuels could be attributed to the fluctuating fuel prices and limited access to

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modern energy sources like liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and electricity (Mani, Jain, Tripathi, and Gould, 2020). Assessing the traditional biomass as energy source, such as charcoal, in this Zaria is critical for informing policy decisions and promoting sustainable energy transitions at the grassroots level (Nnaji *et al.*, 2012). However, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent of its adoption, its performance compared to traditional fuels, and the factors influencing its use among households in semi-urban areas like Zaria. This study was carried out to assess the use and challenges of charcoal as an energy source for cooking among households in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna State, evaluating factors influencing its use and limitations, and suggest strategies for improved household energy security

Across Sub-Saharan Africa, the use of traditional biomass energy particularly charcoal and fuel wood remains widespread, with studies indicating that about 80% of urban households depend on these sources for cooking and heating (Zulu and Richardson, 2013; Tembo *et al.*, 2015). In Nigeria, 70% of households use fuel wood as the primary cooking energy, with consumption levels rising steadily over the decades (Babanyara, 2010; Sambo, 2005). This pattern is evident in Zaria, where a substantial proportion of households continue to use charcoal for cooking due to its affordability, availability, and ease of use. Charcoal also provides income for many traders and producers within and around Zaria, making it both an essential energy source and an important economic activity. This growing demand for charcoal has contributed significantly to deforestation, forest degradation, and loss of biodiversity, particularly in the Northern Nigeria where desertification, soil erosion, declining soil fertility, and reduced agricultural productivity are increasingly evident. (Ekpo and Mba, 2020). This practice undermines forest conservation efforts and exacerbates climate change through the release of greenhouse gases during both production and combustion processes. Despite the ongoing National and International advocacy for cleaner and more sustainable cooking energy sources such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), electricity, and improved cookstoves, the continued reliance on charcoal suggests the presence of underlying economic, cultural, and infrastructural constraints (Roche *et al.*, 2024). Factors such as income level, household size, availability of alternative energy sources, cost fluctuations, and user preferences may strongly influence the choice of charcoal over other cooking fuels. Although charcoal consumption is clearly visible in households and markets across Zaria, there is limited empirical, location-specific evidence on the extent of its use, patterns of consumption, household expenditure, and the factors influencing continued dependence. The absence of such data constrains effective local planning and the development of targeted interventions aimed at reducing environmental pressure while improving household energy security. Therefore, an assessment of charcoal as a cooking

energy source among households in Zaria is necessary to provide evidence-based insights for sustainable energy policy, environmental management, and public health planning.

The objectives of the study are to,

- i. Determine the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents.
- ii. Assess the extent of the use of charcoal in the study area.
- iii. Assess the effects of the use of charcoal in the study area.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of study Area

Zaria, a local government area of Kaduna State, is situated in the Northern Guinea Savannah ecological zone. Kaduna State is located between latitude 9° N and longitude 6° E of the prime meridian. The state has a population of about 6,066,562 people with a total land mass of 45,456.7 sq. km and arable land of 2.02 million hectares (National Population Commission, 2006). The State is characterized by alternating dry and wet seasons with an annual rainfall range between 1270 and 1524 mm. The rainy season extends from April to early October. The dry season extends from November to April. With a mean maximum temperature ranging from 27° C in the rainy season to 35° C in the dry season. This condition is suitable for the crops grown in the state. The major crops grown include sorghum, maize, millet, cotton, groundnut, cowpea, onion, rice, ginger, and vegetables. Livestock kept include cattle, goats, pigs, sheep, and poultry.

2.2. Data Collection and Sampling

Structured questionnaires were used to elicit primary data from household heads, such as demographic characteristics, charcoal usage, and frequency, as well as challenges of charcoal use, from 5 wards, namely, Tudun Wada, Kufena, Gyallesu, Kwarbai, and Kaura, of Zaria LGA of Kaduna State. In each ward, 30 questionnaires were randomly administered to household heads, giving a total of 150 questionnaires from the 5 wards.

2.3. Data Analysis

Data obtained using questionnaires from household heads were subjected to descriptive statistics; frequencies, percentages, and means were used to describe the parameters in the questionnaire. Chi-square tests and logistic regression were applied to test associations between variables (e.g., income level and usage of charcoal). All data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (SPSS Inc., 2010).

3.0 Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics (Table 1) showed that 53.3% of respondents were male, with 56.7%, with age range of 31–50. This indicates that the respondents were among the economically active adults who make energy decisions for the household. This is like the report

presented by (Ogunleye & Afolabi, 2018). While 40% of the respondents earned between ₦30,000 and ₦60,000 monthly, 20% earned below ₦30,000, suggesting that household energy decisions were constrained by limited income in a sizable portion of the population. Typically, low- to lower-middle-income earners. For them, cost is a primary determinant of energy choice. Additionally, cleaner and more efficient energy sources like liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) or electricity may be considered too expensive due to high initial costs (e.g., gas cylinder, stove), along with recurrent costs (e.g., gas refills, prepaid

electricity units). Hence, many of these households opt for charcoal, which is perceived as cheaper and more economical over time and can be purchased in smaller, manageable quantities, making it more accessible for daily or weekly use compared to lump-sum payments for LPG.

In the study area, 33.3% of the respondents were graduates of secondary education, and 29.3% attained tertiary education. This indicates that the level of educational attainment could be attributed to continuous use of traditional fuels such as charcoal as energy for cooking technologies, as supported by Adamu *et al.* (2020).

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency's	Percentages
Gender	Male	80	53.30
	Female	70	46.7
Educational Level	Primary	34	22.7
	Secondary	50	33.3
	Tertiary	44	29.3
	Non	22	14.8
Age of Household Head (Years) <30		30	20.0
	30-50	85	56.7
	>50	35	23.3
Income (₦)	<30,000	45	30.0
	30,000-60,000	60	40.0
	60,000.00-100,000	30	20.0
	>100,000	15	10.0
Usage of Charcoal	Yes	90	60.0
	No	60	40.0
Challenge of Charcoal Use	High cost	60	40.0
	Health issues	45	30.0
	Environmental concerns	25	16.7
	Limited availability	15	10.0
	No problems reported	5	3.30

The level of charcoal use (60%) as an energy source suggests that charcoal is a dominant energy source among households in Zaria. This level of reliance reflects limited access to or affordability of alternative fuels such as LPG or electricity. Cultural attachment and long-standing familiarity with charcoal as a traditional cooking fuel, coupled with infrastructural limitations such as unreliable electricity supply and inadequate access to liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) distribution networks. This indicates that charcoal was the primary cooking fuel for most households, possibly due to low cost compared to LPG or other barriers when compared to 40% of the respondents that do not use charcoal.

The observed charcoal use by respondents in the study area may be due to the fact that charcoal produces less smoke. These attributes are essential in minimizing indoor air pollution, a major health risk from traditional biomass use (WHO, 2021). Despite the positive attributes, several

challenges were identified, such as health concerns (30%) and environmental concerns (16.7%).

The chi-square test results indicate that gender, educational level, and household income are all significantly associated with the use of charcoal as a cooking energy source. Table 2 shows a statistically significant relationship between gender and charcoal use ($p < 0.05$). Among respondents that use charcoal, 48% are male and 52% are female, while a higher percentage of non-users are male (66.7%) compared to females (33.3%). This finding implies that women are slightly more likely to use charcoal for cooking than men. This could be attributed to gender roles in domestic responsibilities in many Nigerian households, where women are more directly involved in food preparation and may thus have a stronger preference or necessity for using charcoal, especially where alternatives are unaffordable or unavailable. There is a highly significant

association ($p < 0.01$) between education level and charcoal use. 24% of the respondents had non-formal education, 28% had primary education, and 48% had secondary education or higher. In contrast, a greater proportion of non-users had non-formal (33.3%) or primary education (33.3%), with only 25% having secondary education or higher. This suggests that individuals with higher levels of education are more likely to use charcoal than those with little or no formal education. This finding may seem counterintuitive since

higher education is often associated with higher income and awareness of energy options. However, it may reflect limited access to alternatives even among the relatively educated, or it may indicate that charcoal remains a perceived "efficient" and readily available option even among middle-income earners.

Household income also shows a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) with charcoal use. A larger proportion of charcoal users (36%) fall into the low-income category

Table 2: Chi-Square Test Results for Association between Socioeconomic Characteristics and Use of Charcoal

Socio-economic Characteristics	Categories	Charcoal Use	Don't Use Charcoal	Chi -Square	P-value	Significance
Gender	Male	60(48%)	40(66.7%)	5.23	0.022	*
	Female	66(52%)	20(33.3%)			
Educational level	Non-Formal	30 (24.0%)	20 (33.3%)	12.45	0.006	**
	Primary	35(28.0%)	20 (33.3%)			
	Secondary+	60 (48.0%)	15 (25.0%)			
Houshold Income (₦)	Low (<₦30,000)	45 (36.0%)	35 (58.3%)	10.78	0.013	*
	30,000-60,000	50 (40%)	20 (33.3%)			
	>60,000	30 (24.0%)	5(8.3%)			

** Coefficient statistically significant at 1% level

(<₦30,000), while only 24% earn more than ₦60,000. In contrast, among non-users, 58.3% earn below ₦30,000, and only 8.3% earn above ₦60,000. This suggests that income is a strong determinant of charcoal use. Those with lower incomes are more dependent on charcoal, possibly due to the relatively low cost and accessibility of charcoal compared to cleaner alternatives such as LPG or electricity. However, the data also indicate that a substantial number of middle-income households (₦30,000 – ₦60,000) also use charcoal (40%), highlighting that charcoal use cuts across income groups in varying degrees. Higher-income households are less likely to rely on charcoal and may use LPG, electricity, or other modern energy sources. This finding is consistent with the findings of Akintunde *et al.* (2019), which emphasized that affordability remains a key determinant of energy choice in Nigeria.

A binary logistic regression was conducted to assess the influence of selected socio-economic characteristics on the likelihood of using charcoal as a cooking energy source. The model yielded an $R = 0.443$ and $R^2 = 0.325$, indicating that about 32.5% of the variation in charcoal use can be explained by the socio-economic variables included in the model. (Table 3). Male-headed households were significantly

less likely to use charcoal compared to female-headed households (OR = 0.45; 95% CI: 0.22–0.92; $p = 0.029$). This implies that male-headed households are 55% less likely to use charcoal compared to female-headed households. This suggests that female-headed households are more dependent on charcoal, likely due to economic vulnerability, single income streams, or lower access to clean energy alternatives. This aligns with studies by Akinbami *et al.* (2001). This highlight gender disparities in energy poverty and decision-making. Income showed a strong and statistically significant relationship with charcoal use.

Households earning above ₦60,000 (OR = 4.67, CI: 1.98–11.02, $p = 0.001$ **) were more likely to use charcoal than those earning less than ₦30,000 ($p = 0.001$), and those in the ₦30,000–₦60,000 range were twice as likely ($p = 0.036$). Both income brackets showed significant positive associations with charcoal use, especially the >₦60,000 group, who were nearly 5 times more likely to use charcoal compared to those earning less than ₦30,000. This result is somewhat surprising, as higher income is generally expected to increase access to cleaner fuels like LPG.

Table. 3: Logistic Regression Relationship between Socioeconomic Characteristics and the Likelihood of Using Charcoal as a Cooking Energy Source.

Variable	Categories	Odds Ratio (OR)	(5% Confidence Interval)	P-value	Significance
Gender of Household Head		0.45	0.22--0.92	0.029	*
Education	Primary	1.75	0.85--3.60	0.128	NS
	Secondary	3.33	1.62-- 6.85	0.001	**
Household Income (₦)	30,000-60,000.	2.1	0.62--2.40	0.036	*
	>60,000	4.67	1.98--11.02	0.001	**
Household Head Age	30–50	1.15	0.55-- 2.42	0.712	NS
	>50	1.8	0.75--4.32	0.190	NS

$R = 0.443$

$R^2 = 0.325$

** Coefficient statistically significant at 1% level

NS: not signification

While higher odds might appear to indicate greater use, it's likely that these groups are using cleaner charcoal alternatives rather than reverting to firewood or kerosene. Alternatively, the result may also reflect charcoal's transitional role as a bridge between traditional and modern fuels.

4. Conclusion

Charcoal remains a widely used energy source. The high usage underscores its affordability, accessibility, and cultural familiarity in the face of rising costs and limited availability of alternative fuels such as LPG and electricity. Households earning between ₦30,000 and ₦60,000 showed a stronger tendency to rely on charcoal due to the high upfront costs of cleaner fuels, irregular electricity supply, and the flexibility of purchasing charcoal in small quantities. Charcoal usage is both a coping strategy and a reflection of persistent energy poverty, particularly among low- and lower-middle-income households.

Recommendations:

- Government and development partners should subsidize LPG starter kits (cylinders, burners, regulators) to lower the entry barrier for low-income households.
- Encourage the use of improved biomass cookstoves that are more efficient and produce less smoke.
- Launch community-based campaigns on the health hazards of charcoal use, especially indoor air pollution, and the benefits of cleaner alternatives.
- Government should regulate and monitor charcoal production to minimize unsustainable harvesting of forest resources.
- Promote the adoption of sustainably sourced or carbonized charcoal as a transitional option for households not yet able to switch to clean energy

Abbreviations

LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
OR	Odd Ratio
CL	Confidence Interval
WHO	Word Health Organization

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Author Contributions

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Conflicts of Interest

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